

THE ROLE OF THE KIPCHAKS AND KYRGYZ IN THE POLITICAL LIFE OF THE KOKAND KHANATE

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Abstract: This article discusses the issue of the role of Kyrgyz and Kipchaks in the socio-political life of the Kokhan Khanate.

Key words: Khanate of Kokhan, Sheralikhon, Mallakhon. Kyrgyz, Kazakhs, Fazilbiy, Muslimqul, Tokmoq, Jacket, Marka.

In terms of studying the history of the Uzbek khanates, the Kokan Khanate is a country whose history is little studied. Because the sources created during the reign of the Kokhan Khanate were hardly studied during the period of Tsarist Russia and the Soviet states. By the years of independence, interest in the political history of the Koqan khanate, mutual relations, lifestyle, and ethnic relations of the peoples living in it began, and many Uzbek historians began to research the history of the khanate. V. Ploskikh and A. Hasanov also contributed to the study of the history of the Kokan khanate¹. For example, A. Hasanov in his candidate thesis and monograph "People's movements in Kyrgyzstan during the Kokhan Khanate" (1961), V.M. Ploskikh tried to explain step by step the relationship between the Kokhan Khanate and the Kyrgyz people in the book "Kirgizi i Kokandskoe khanstvo" (1977). The presented works reflect the subjection of the Kyrgyz to the Kokhan Khanate, their role in the political life of the Khanate, and their struggle against the tyranny of the Khans².

In the 20s of the 18th centuries, the city of Khojand, which belonged to the Kokhan Khanate, was ruled by Aqbotabi Kyrgyz, one of the Kyrgyz nobles. After Abdurahimbi took over the governorship of Khojand, he was killed as a result of a conspiracy during the struggle for power. Tajiks and Kyrgyz had a great position in the social and political life of the Kokan Khanate. They were a great force in the Khan's army. The Kipchaks, who consider themselves to be one of the 92 Uzbek tribes, had a much greater place in the Kokhan Khanate. Kyrgyz mainly moved and engaged in cattle breeding in the mountains around Fergana and mountain basins like Ketmontepa Oloy. The influence of Kyrgyz and Kipchaks in the socio-political life of their country has increased over time³.

The rise of the status of Kyrgyz nobles in the social and political life of the Kokand Khanate is connected with the name of the Kokand Khan Abdulkarimbi. During his rule, the Khanate of Jung'or (Oirat), which was established in the north of the country, began to invade the lands of the Khanate. In 1741, the attacks of the Dzhungar tribes on the Fergana valley began. In such a situation, Abdulkarimbi fought against them with the support of the Kyrgyz-Kipchak tribes and the governor of Oratepa, Fazilbi, and expelled the Dzhungars from the territory of the country in 1745. This leads to an increase in the political influence of the

¹ Hasanov A. People's movements in Kyrgyzstan during the Kokan Khanate. - T.: 1961. P.26

² Плоских В.М. Киргизы и Кокандское ханство. Бишкек. 1977

³ Боотаева Б. Кыргызы между Кокандом, Китаем и Россией. Бишкек. Илим. 1995. С. 19.

Kipchak and Kyrgyz tribes in the country and to a certain acceleration of the process of their migration to the Fergana Valley. In 1745, the Uzbek-Kyrgyz alliance was formed for the first time against the Dzhungar tribes who invaded the Fergana valley. In the same year, Khan Galden-Seren of the Dzungars, with the help of the Sin Empire, sent his two main commanders, Septen and Khoton, to the Fergana Valley. At that time, the Kyrgyz army of 1,000 people and Kokan's irregular army fought against 10 small cannons and an army of 20,000 people. As a result of this war, the army of the Dzhungars was defeated and more than half of them were destroyed.

However, the fight against the Jungors was not always successful. According to the author of "History of Shahruhi", Abdulkarimbi was defeated by the Jungars and even had to send his son Bobobek to them as a hostage. But this dependency lasted for a short time and Abdulkarimbi managed to restore his rule in Kokan. Kyrgyz living in remote areas of Ferghana Valley continue to fight against Jungors. In 1748, they managed to defeat the Dzhungar army led by Dorji. In the spring of 1749, the army of the Jungians led by Lama-Dorji was defeated by the Kyrgyz.

From the middle of the 18th century, the military power of the Kokhan Khanate increased, and the process of expanding the territory of the country at the expense of the neighboring regions intensified. By the time of Erdanabi's rule, the military alliance established during Abdulkarimbi's time is replaced by the policy of annexing the territories inhabited by Kyrgyz to the Khanate. As a result of mutual feudal wars between the Kyrgyz, the military potential of these tribes has greatly decreased, besides, the mutual wars between the Kyrgyz tribes create an unstable situation in the northeastern part of the khanate, which makes Erdanabi stop the mutual wars in these areas. He had caused them to march against them in order to kill them. In 1762, Erdanabi's troops occupied the city of Ozgan. In such a situation, the Kyrgyz tribes, Adigans and Mongols, revolted under the leadership of Hajibi. Erdanabi troops suppressed this uprising. In this way, the cities of Ozgan and Osh will be included in the Kokand Khanate⁴.

By the beginning of the 19th century, the Sin dynasty of the Manchus ruling China imposed excessive taxes on the Kalmyk, Uyghur, Kyrgyz, Karakalpak and Kazakh Kipchak tribes living in Eastern Turkestan and interfered in their internal politics. begins to move. The Kokhan Khanate entered a period of political instability from the 40s of the 19th century, and this situation continued until 1876. Naturally, this situation led to the weakening of the khanate. As a result, in addition to Uzbek tribal chiefs, large nobles of many nations began to interfere in the political life of the khanate. Among these tribes, from the 40s of the XIX century, Kipchaks and Kyrgyz began to gain special influence. This situation caused the political situation in the khanate to derail and enter the era of mutual massacres.

The great influence of Kyrgyz and Kipchak tribes in the internal life of the khanate in the Kokand Khanate is connected with the name of the Kokand Khan Sheralikhon. During his reign, the Kipchak tribes gained great influence in the khanate and became a serious political force. One of the chieftains of the Kipchak tribe took over the country's management by taking the position of Muslim-Qul thousand-bashi. In 1842, when Amir Nasrullah conquered the Khanate of Kokhan, political instability arose in the Khanate. The reason for this is that Amir Nasrullah's appointed viceroy of Kokand, Ibrahim Dodkhoh, began to collect from the

⁴ Ботаева Б. Кыргызы между Кокандом, Китаем и Россией. Бишкек. Илим. 1995. С. 21

population the taxes introduced in the Bukhara Emirate, in addition to the existing taxes in the khanate. As a result, the standard of living of the country's population decreased, and the people suffered a lot. Such a situation would have a negative impact on the socio-economic situation of the country. By 1842, a candidate for the khanate throne was not found among the descendants of Norbotabi, and when Sheralikhan, who grew up among the Kyrgyz from his youth, took the khanate throne, the position of the Kyrgyz nobles in the country increased⁵.

In the early days of Khudoyar Khan's reign, he did not interfere in any state affairs. Because Muslimkul did not want him to have contact with anyone, he did not allow him to go out of the khan's circle. Thus, all the power in the khanate was concentrated in the hands of Muslim. By 1853, the situation changed radically. With the help of an army summoned from Tashkent, Khudoyar Khan organizes the "Kipchak massacre" in order to end the rule of the Kipchaks in the khanate. As a result of this massacre, 20 thousand Kipchaks were killed. Thus, in the history of the khanate, the Muslim rule was abolished, and the position of the Kipchaks weakened.

During the reign of Mallakhan (1858-1862), the major government positions in the khanate were mainly occupied by Kyrgyz. For example, he appointed O'tamboi Koshbegi to Tashkent hokimiy, Bobobek Dodkhoh Kyrgyz to Khojand hokimiy, and Shodmonkhoja to Baliqchi hokimiy. During the reign of Mallakhan, the position of Alimkul, another nobleman of the Kyrgyz and Kipchaks, increased. He became one of Khanning's trusted and close people. Alimkul rose from the position of doorkeeper to the rank of minister in the khanate⁶.

In the matters of Public Administration of the Khanate, in addition to mainly Uzbek tribal chiefs, Kipchak and Kyrgyz tribal chiefs also held a leading position. The major provinces and stations in the Khanate were ruled by the closest nobles of the Khan. These provinces and principalities were considered the major economic-political and governing centers of the Khanate. Sheralikhan comes to the throne of the Khanate of Kokand in 1842. The main role in his seizure of power in Kokand is played by a nobleman named Joseph of the Kyrgyz nobility. Sheralikhan appoints Yusuf as the sardar of the mingboshi and Khanate armies. Sheralikhan's initial implementation would establish a new management system in major central cities and major provinces. Local nobles and Kyrgyz feudal lords become the mainstay of the Khan. In the early days, there were hardly any high public offices and high positions in the Khanate. As periods passed, the number of senior officials increased. Their power depended on the level of influence of the close officials of Khan and Khan. For example, Khudoyarkhan cancels many public positions after fully assuming power. A number of senior positions – mingboshi, koshbegi, etc. - abolish the administration of the provinces, while handing over the administration of the provinces to Beks appointed from their closest ones⁷.

The subjugation of Kyrgyz-inhabited territories to the Khanate of Kokand was carried out mainly during the reigns of Norbutabi, Olimkhan, Umar Khan and Muhammad Alikhan. In order to strengthen the administrative management system of the Khanate, mainly military fortresses were built in the territories inhabited by Kyrgyz. Among them are the weaving, Kurtka, Marka, Darut-Qurgon, Jungal. These regions were considered to be major centers of Kyrgyz administration and were ruled by the major nobles of the country. In the wake of

⁵ Мхаммаддаҳакимхон тўра. Мунтахаб ат-таворих. -Т.: Yangi asr avlodi., 2010. Б. 677.

⁶ Бобобеков Х. Қўқон тарихи. -Т.: Фан. 1996. Б. 33-34.

⁷ Muhammad Yunus Toib. Tarixi Alimquli Amirlashkar. Sharq yulduzi 1996. 1-son. Б. 22

increasing taxes, Kyrgyz March to the Fergana Valley and demand a unified citizenship from the Khanate. Civil cases of Kyrgyz were recorded in the populous regions of Tashkent and Andijan. As a result of the increasing tax policy of the Khanate by the 60s of the XIX century, Kyrgyz who live in the northeastern part of the country try to start relations with Russia. The burukchi tribe of the Kyrgyz take control of the Kurtka fortress, which is located in the Norin Valley. As a result, in 1865, representatives of Russian diplomacy begin negotiations on the question of using the tumultuous situations in the Kokand Khanate to include the territory of Jungal as part of the Russian Empire⁸.

In conclusion, it can be noted that the process of adding Kipchak and Kyrgyz tribes to the composition of the Kokand Khanate began as early as the formation of the Khanate. The inclusion of Kipchaks and Kyrgyz in the Khanate had a positive effect on their socio-economic activities. From the 18th century, the life of the Kipchak and Kyrgyz tribes, who were exclusively engaged in animal husbandry, also began to enter industries such as crafts, agriculture and trade. They began to be confused with different areas of crafts when it came to the middle of the XVIII century. The introduction of Khanate forms of government into the life of the Kipchak and Kyrgyz tribes led to the improvement of control systems in both Kipchak and Kyrgyz. In the Kipchaks and Kyrgyz, layers of tribal-lead elders were formed. The inclusion of Kipchaks and Kyrgyz in the Khanate led to the widespread spread of Islam among them, the expansion of the social composition of the population, the implementation of relations between them on the basis of a certain order rule.

⁸ Плоских В. М. Киргизы и Кокандское ханство. Фрунзе. Илим. 1977. С. 109.

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